
Warming trends and long-range dependent climate variability since year 1900: a Bayesian approach

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2 ABSTRACT

3 Temporal persistence in unforced climate variability makes detection of trends in surface
4 temperature difficult. Part of the challenge is methodological since standard techniques assume
5 a separation of time scales between trend and noise. In this work we present a novel Bayesian
6 approach to trend detection under the assumption of long-range dependent natural variability,
7 and we use estimates of historical forcing to test if the method correctly discriminates trends
8 from low-frequency natural variability. As an application we analyze $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ gridded data from the
9 GISS Surface Temperature Analysis. In the time period from 1900 to 2015 we find positive trends
10 for 99% of the grid points. For 84% of the grid points we are confident that the trend is positive,
11 meaning that the 95% credibility interval for the temperature trend contained only positive values.
12 This number increased to 89% when we used estimates of historical forcing to specify the noise
13 model. For the time period from 1900 to 1985 the corresponding ratios were 42% and 52%. Our
14 findings demonstrate that positive trends since 1900 are now detectable locally over most of
15 Earth's surface.

16 **Keywords:** Trend detection, climate change, long-range dependence, fractional Gaussian noise, Bayesian methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

17 Since the year 1900, the global mean surface temperature (GMST) has increased by almost 1 degree K
18 due to increasing concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. While we are far from a full
19 understanding of the complex dynamics of Earth's climate, the cause of the industrial-era warming is well
20 understood, and the question of detection of global warming is today of little relevance. Recent detection
21 studies for global temperature have instead focused on identifying the onset time of the anthropogenic
22 warming, as well as the time when the warming became statistically detectable (Abram et al., 2016). For
23 local and regional temperatures the situation is different. Not all of Earth's surface has warmed since 1900,
24 and in some locations the warming is small compared to the natural variability. Sutton et al. (2015) point
25 out that the question of local detectability is highly relevant since it provides insight into the strength of the
26 warming signal relative to the natural fluctuations for which ecosystems are adapted.

27 From a statistical point of view, temperature trends provide a unique challenge since the climate naturally
28 fluctuates on an extended range of time scales. A standard set-up is to assume that a temperature anomaly

29 time series $\Delta T(t)$ can be approximated by a model on the form

$$30 \quad \Delta T(t) = m(t) + \varepsilon(t), \quad (1)$$

31 where $m(t) = a + bt$ is a linear trend, and $\varepsilon(t)$ is a stochastic process (Bloomfield, 1992). In the
32 zero-dimensional global energy-balance model (EBM),

$$33 \quad C\Delta T = -\lambda\Delta Tdt + F(t)dt + \sigma_{\text{OU}}dB(t), \quad (2)$$

34 the unforced temperature fluctuations $\varepsilon(t)$ are defined by the equation $Cd\varepsilon = -\lambda\varepsilon dt + \sigma_{\text{OU}}dB(t)$, which
35 describes an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck (OU) process (the continuous interpretation of a first-order auto-regressive
36 (AR1) process) with a characteristic correlation scale $\tau = C/\lambda$:

$$37 \quad \varepsilon(t) = \frac{\sigma_{\text{OU}}}{C} \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-(t-s)/\tau} dB(s).$$

38 In the equations above, C is the average heat capacity of Earth's surface, λ is the feedback parameter, and
39 $F(t)$ is a forcing record. For this model, parameter estimates in temperature time series yield values of τ
40 that are much shorter than those relevant for the warming trend. Hence, there is a separation of time scales
41 that makes it easy to estimate the characteristics of the noise process without influence from the long-term
42 trend. However, the zero-dimensional EBM in Equation (2) does not model the slow thermal response of
43 the deep oceans, and the generalization to the so-called 2-box EBM (Geoffroy et al., 2013) gives a noise
44 model on the form

$$45 \quad \varepsilon(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t G(t-s)dB(s),$$

46 where the response function $G(t) = c_1e^{-t/\tau_1} + c_2e^{-t/\tau_2}$ is a sum of two exponential functions. The
47 generalization to N -box models gives response functions that are sums of N exponential functions.
48 Models with multiple characteristic time scales are consistent with observations. Estimated power spectral
49 densities (PSDs) of temperature reconstructions show approximate scale invariance, i.e. $S(f) \sim f^{-\beta}$, for
50 frequencies corresponding to time scales from months to several hundred thousand years (Rypdal and
51 Rypdal, 2016). Analyses of the relation between reconstructed forcing and reconstructed temperatures, as
52 well as experiments in Earth System Models (ESMs), show approximate scale invariance in the climate
53 response and in unforced climate variability on time scales from months to several hundred years (Rypdal
54 and Rypdal, 2014; Rypdal et al., 2018). The implication for trend detection is that the noise processes that
55 represent natural variability should be allowed to exhibit long-range dependence (LRD). A parsimonious
56 model with LRD is obtained by using a power-law response function $G(t) = (t/\mu)^{\beta/2-1}$. With this choice,
57 the noise model $\varepsilon(t)$ is a fractional Gaussian noise (fGn). The parameter β is identical to the exponent in
58 the PSD and related to the so-called Hurst exponent via the relation $\beta = 2H - 1$.

59 We write the discrete-time version of Equation (1) on the following vector form:

$$60 \quad \mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)^\top = (m(t_1) + \varepsilon(t_1), \dots, m(t_n) + \varepsilon(t_n))^\top, \quad (3)$$

61 where \mathbf{y} is the temperature time series. Using the short-hand notation $\varepsilon_i = \varepsilon(t_i)$, the vector $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} =$
62 $(\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n)^\top$ is a zero-mean stationary Gaussian process with covariance function:

$$63 \quad \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_i, \varepsilon_j) = \frac{\sigma_\varepsilon^2}{2} (|i - j + 1|^{2H} + |i - j - 1|^{2H} + |i - j|^{2H}). \quad (4)$$

64 Several previous studies have modeled climatic data using a linear trend model $m(t_i) = a + bt_i$,
65 $i = 1, \dots, n$, and an LRD noise term (Cohn and Lins, 2005; Koutsoyiannis and Montanari, 2007; Franzke,
66 2012; Løvsletten and Rypdal, 2016). Some of these studies conclude that trends that have been identified as
67 statistically significant based on AR1 noise models, are not found to be significant when LRD noise models
68 are used. Ideally, the parameters in the noise model (the Hurst exponent H and the scale parameter σ_ε)
69 and the parameters in the trend model (the intercept a and the slope b) should be estimated simultaneously,
70 but most previous studies have used non-parametric measures of the second-order statistics to determine
71 the Hurst exponent. A standard approach is to estimate a trend using a least-squares method, and to
72 subsequently estimate a Hurst exponent and a scale parameter of the de-trended signal using a fluctuation
73 function over a range of time scales. The fluctuation function could be a wavelet-based fluctuation function,
74 a variogram, the de-trended fluctuation (DFA) function, or the PSD. The significance of a positive trend
75 can then be tested using Monte-Carlo simulations, or by theoretical estimates based on the specified
76 noise model. The disadvantage of the two-step approach is that it does not fully take into account the
77 dependence between the estimates of the trend and the estimates of the noise parameters. Part of the
78 reason why fluctuation-based estimators of H and σ_ε are popular is that likelihood-based methods are
79 computationally costly for processes with LRD. Computing the likelihood function involves inversions of
80 the dense covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ defined by the elements $\Sigma_{ij} = \text{Cov}(\varepsilon_i, \varepsilon_j)$ in Equation (4).

81 In this paper we take advantage of recent work by Sørbye et al. (2018) who incorporate fGn models within
82 a Bayesian hierarchical formulation using the computational framework of latent Gaussian models. These
83 models can be analysed efficiently using the methodology of integrated nested Laplace approximation
84 (INLA) developed in Rue et al. (2009). The INLA methodology provides accurate estimates of the posterior
85 marginal distributions for all of the model parameters which can then be used to calculate summary statistics
86 like posterior means, variances, credible intervals and posterior probabilities. Of particular interest is the
87 posterior marginal distribution $p(b | \mathbf{y})$, which is used to calculate the probability $\text{Prob}[b > 0 | \mathbf{y}]$ of a
88 positive trend given the observed temperature anomalies \mathbf{y} . The Bayesian modeling approach is described
89 further in section 2. In section 3 we discuss an alternative approach to trend detection where data of
90 historical forcing is used to discriminate between forced response and natural variability. The results of
91 the latter is used to test and validate the methods described in section 2. Results of analyses of gridded
92 temperature data from the GISS Surface Temperature Analysis are presented in section 4, and discussed in
93 section 5.

2 BAYESIAN INFERENCE

94 To analyse the regression model defined by Equation (3) for a large number of gridded time series,
95 computational efficiency is crucial. The presented Bayesian approach makes use of the computational
96 framework of latent Gaussian models. These models can be seen as a flexible class of three-stage Bayesian
97 hierarchical models where the different stages specify the distribution of an observational vector \mathbf{y} , a
98 Gaussian prior for a latent random field \mathbf{x} and priors for random hyperparameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The first stage
99 of the model assumes that the observations are conditionally independent given the latent field and the

100 hyperparameters. The resulting joint conditional distribution of the observations is then expressed as the
 101 product of the marginals:

$$102 \quad p(\mathbf{y} \mid \mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\theta}) = p(y_1 \mid x_1, \boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdots p(y_n \mid x_n, \boldsymbol{\theta}).$$

103 In our case, the observations are assumed to have a Gaussian distribution and the marginals are just
 104 univariate Gaussian distributions.

105 The second stage of the latent Gaussian model formulation specifies that the conditional distribution of \mathbf{x}
 106 given $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is a Gaussian random field. Based on the regression formulation in Equation (3), the expectation
 107 of \mathbf{y} is modelled in terms of a linear predictor, $\boldsymbol{\eta} = E(\mathbf{y})$. The latent field \mathbf{x} includes all the random
 108 variables of the predictor $\mathbf{x} = (a, b, \boldsymbol{\epsilon})^\top$. By assigning Gaussian priors to all of these variables, \mathbf{x} will
 109 also be Gaussian and this is what separates a latent Gaussian model from general three-stage Bayesian
 110 hierarchical models. The conditional distribution of \mathbf{x} given hyperparameters is then defined by

$$111 \quad \mathbf{x} \mid \boldsymbol{\theta} \sim \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, \mathbf{Q}^{-1}) \quad (5)$$

112 where $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ denotes the mean vector and \mathbf{Q} is the precision (inverse covariance) matrix of all the random
 113 variables in \mathbf{x} . The matrix \mathbf{Q} reflects conditional independence properties of the elements in \mathbf{x} , giving zeros
 114 for all combinations of elements x_i and x_j that are independent conditioned on the other elements of \mathbf{x} .
 115 Usually, \mathbf{x} is assumed to be a Gaussian Markov random field (GMRF) implying that the precision matrix
 116 \mathbf{Q} will be sparse.

117 The final stage of the model formulation specifies priors for the hyperparameters which here include
 118 $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (H, \sigma_\epsilon)$. Assuming independent priors, the probability density function is $p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = p(H)p(\sigma_\epsilon)$ where
 119 both parameters are assigned penalised complexity priors (Simpson et al., 2017; Sørbye and Rue, 2017).
 120 Using Bayes theorem, the posterior joint distribution of the latent field and the hyperparameters is expressed
 121 as

$$122 \quad p(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{x} \mid \mathbf{y}) \propto \prod_{i=1}^n p(y_i \mid x_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}) p(\mathbf{x} \mid \boldsymbol{\theta}) p(H) p(\sigma_\epsilon). \quad (6)$$

123 The main aim of the current analysis is to find the posterior marginal distributions $p(b \mid \mathbf{y})$, $p(H \mid \mathbf{y})$
 124 and $p(\sigma_\epsilon \mid \mathbf{y})$. These distributions are then used to find summary statistics for the parameters. Especially,
 125 significance of warming trends are assessed by the probability of $b > 0$ according to the density $p(b \mid \mathbf{y})$.
 126 More generally, posterior marginal distributions for all components of \mathbf{x} and the hyperparameters in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$
 127 might be of interest. Theoretically, such marginals are expressed by integrating out all other variables in
 128 Equation (6), but this is not a computationally feasible approach. Posterior samples from the posterior
 129 marginals can be obtained using Markov chain Monte Carlo approaches (Gamerman and Lopes, 2006),
 130 but this is computationally slow as such approaches are simulation-based. The INLA methodology (Rue
 131 et al., 2009) represents an accurate and computationally superior alternative as it estimates the posterior
 132 marginals without any simulations, combining numerical approximations with numerical interpolation and
 133 integration, see Rue et al. (2017) for a recent review. In order for INLA to be computationally fast, the latent
 134 field \mathbf{x} needs to be a GMRF having a sparse precision matrix \mathbf{Q} in Equation (5). This is not the case when
 135 the noise term $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is fGn having an LRD structure, but the precision matrix of an AR1 process is tridiagonal.
 136 In Sørbye et al. (2018), the fGn process is approximated using a weighted sum of AR1 processes where the
 137 weights and the first-lag autocorrelation coefficients of the approximation are optimized to match the exact
 138 covariance function of fGn defined in Equation (4). For the time scales of interest, the approximation is

139 very accurate using a sum of only four AR1 processes. This speeds up the model fitting of Equation (3)
 140 considerably, see section 4 for results.

3 USING HISTORICAL FORCING TO SPECIFY NOISE MODELS

141 The alternative approach to trend detection that we present in this paper makes use of the historical global
 142 data of radiative forcing $F(t)$ (an updated version of the forcing in Hansen et al. (2011)). This is done to
 143 validate the results of the approach in section 2 which does not account for information about radiative
 144 forcing. For the EBM in Equation (2), the forced temperature response is

$$145 \quad \Delta T(t) = \frac{1}{C} \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-(t-s)/\tau} F(s) ds + \frac{\sigma_{OU}}{C} \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-(t-s)/\tau} dB(s).$$

146 where $\varepsilon(t)$ is an OU model with characteristic correlation length τ and

$$147 \quad m(t) = \frac{1}{C} \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-(t-s)/\tau} F(s) ds$$

148 is a convolution of the exponential kernel $e^{-t/\tau}$ with the historical forcing.

149 Rypdal and Rypdal (2014) proposed an LRD modification of this model in discrete time where ε in
 150 Equation (3) is an fGn process with Hurst exponent H , variance σ_ε^2 , and mean function

$$151 \quad m(t_i) = \sigma_f \sum_{s=-\infty}^{t_i} (t_i - s)^{H-3/2} (F_0 + F(s)), \quad i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (7)$$

152 The parameter F_0 is introduced to make sure that the forcing records $F(t_i)$ have the correct mean as
 153 this a relative measure, while σ_f is an additional scaling parameter. Myrvoll-Nilsen et al. (2019) extend
 154 the methodology described in section 2 to analyse models where the fGn process has mean defined
 155 by Equation (7). This approach is more computationally demanding as it introduces the additional
 156 hyperparameters σ_f and F_0 , such that $\theta = (H, \sigma_\varepsilon, \sigma_f, F_0)$.

157 Fig. 1 shows surface temperature anomalies from two grid points, one located around the city of Moscow
 158 (55N, 37E), and one location in the tropical Pacific ocean (33S, 120W). The dotted blue lines show the
 159 estimated linear trend $m(t_i) = a + bt_i$ using the methods described in section 2, and the solid black
 160 curves are the estimated forced responses in Equation (7). Using historical forcing implies that we are
 161 imposing a global warming signal, and hence estimates of increasing functions $m(t_i)$ can not be considered
 162 as detection of warming trends. However, our purpose is not to obtain estimates of $m(t_i)$, but rather to
 163 estimate the parameters in the noise term ε when the forced response is modeled more realistically than
 164 a linear function. Hence, our second method for trend detection is to use a linear model $m(t_i) = a + bt_i$
 165 together with a noise model ε , where the parameters σ and H are fixed and equal to the posterior marginal
 166 mean values obtained from the model where $m(t_i)$ is given by Equation (7).

4 RESULTS

167 In this section we present results for $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ gridded data from the GISS Surface Temperature Analysis.
 168 Annual data is used and parameter estimates are given for the time series in the grid point for which there

169 is no more than 5% missing data. We have used the two different methods described in sections 2 and 3,
 170 respectively. Fig. 2 shows maps of estimates for the trend parameter b , and the noise parameters σ_ε and H
 171 for the time period 1900-2015. The presented estimates are the posterior means obtained from the estimated
 172 posterior marginal distributions. The method described in section 2 is used to obtain the estimates in panels
 173 A, C, and E, and the method described in section 3 is used to obtain the estimates in panels B, D, and F. It
 174 is well-known that the Hurst exponents are higher for sea-surface temperatures than for land temperatures
 175 (Monetti et al., 2003; Fraedrich and Blender, 2003; Fredriksen and Rypdal, 2016), and this is confirmed
 176 in this study. We also observe stronger warming trends in the Arctic compared with the rest of Earth's
 177 surface, consistent with polar amplification. Of the 11997 grid points that are analyzed, 11883 and 11906
 178 had positive estimates for the trend parameter b for the two methods, respectively.

179 The two methods presented do give quite similar results for the parameters b , σ_ε , and H , indicating that
 180 the method described in section 2 produces reasonable estimates of the noise parameters. However, Fig. 3
 181 shows that the root mean square error, defined by

$$182 \quad \text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - m(t_i))^2}{n}}, \quad (8)$$

183 is generally higher when a linear trend is used. Hence, the noise processes need to account for more
 184 variability in the models described in section 2 than in the models described in section 3. This effect can
 185 also be seen in Fig. 4, which summarizes the main findings of this work, but the effect is very subtle.
 186 Panels A, C, and E in Fig. 4 show the posterior probability of a positive linear trend given the observed
 187 temperature time series for each grid point using the method described in section 2, and Panels A, C, and E
 188 show the same numbers obtained using the method described in section 3. Panels A and B show results for
 189 the years 1900 to 1950, panels C and D show results for the years 1900 to 1985, and panels E and F show
 190 results for the time period 1900-2015. Using data up to the year 1950 we find $\text{Prob}[b > 0 \mid \mathbf{y}] > 0.95$ for
 191 3571 and 4606 out of the 11997 analyzed grid points, for the two methods respectively. These numbers
 192 increase to 5140 and 6223 is the time period extends to year 1985. And to 10121 and 10683 when the
 193 analysis includes all years from 1900 to 2015. Fig. 4 shows that there are large areas in the oceans where
 194 the sea-surface temperature warming signal has become detectable over the last 30 years.

195 Fitting the model in Equation (3) where the linear trend and the parameters of the fGn model are estimated
 196 simultaneously, required on average 2.7 seconds per time series. This gives a total elapsed computation
 197 time of approximately 9 hours for all 11997 grid points. Using the approach described in section 3, we
 198 first fit an fGn process where the mean is specified by Equation (7). The average run time to fit this model
 199 to a single time series was almost 8 seconds, giving a total run time of approximately 25.9 hours. The
 200 second step of the method in section 3 fits the linear trend combined with the fGn noise term using fixed
 201 parameters. Fitting of this model required on average 1.5 seconds for individual time series, giving a total
 202 elapsed computation time of approximately 5 hours for all grid points. The main reason for the increased
 203 computation time of the approach described in section 3 compared with the method in section 2 is the
 204 increased number of hyperparameters. Also, fitting of the model including radiative forcing required
 205 extensions to existing software, see Myrvoll-Nilsen et al. (2019) for further details.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

206 The main contribution of this paper is to present a computational efficient Bayesian method for trend-
 207 detection under the assumption of LRD noise, and to apply the method to detection of global warming in

208 gridded temperature data. By considering two different methods, where the second uses historical data
209 for global radiative forcing, we validate that the inaccuracy of a linear trend model does not affect the
210 specification of the trend model to such a degree that it significantly affects the trend-detection results.
211 Hence, we avoid a situation where the presence of non-linear temperature trends produce biased estimates
212 of σ_ε and H , which again affect the trend detection.

213 The results presented in this paper, is that even by the most conservative estimates, more than 84% of the
214 analyzed grid points show significant warming at the 0.05-level. This ratio is higher than the 80% ratio that
215 [Løvsletten and Rypdal \(2016\)](#) obtained after making a model selection between AR1 and fGn for each
216 grid point, and much higher than what they obtain for a pure fGn model. Our results also show a striking
217 difference for the time period 1900 to 2015 compared to 1900 to 1985, and clearly demonstrate that even
218 locally, the warming signal has emerged from the noise over the last 30 years.

219 The limitations of the approach presented here is that noise models are restricted to the class of fGns.
220 Whereas LRD models are highly accurate on decadal time scales in GMST, local temperatures exhibit
221 modes of internal variability that are not well-approximated by scale invariance. The most prominent
222 example being the El Niño Souther Oscillation (ENSO). We therefore believe that future work on trend
223 detection in surface temperature data should be based on more flexible models, with more free parameters.
224 The introduction of more flexible models must be weighed against the risk of statistical overfitting for
225 the relatively short instrumental temperature record. An alternative approach is to characterize internal
226 variability as the fluctuations around ensemble means in historical runs in ESMs. Using randomization
227 of phases one can then run Monte-Carlo simulations without specifying parametric models. However,
228 since spatial patterns of internal variability vary between models it is difficult to ensure that the unforced
229 fluctuations in a particular grid point is a good representation of the unforced fluctuations of this grid point
230 in the real climate system.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

231 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
232 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

233 EMN, SHS, HBF and MR designed the study. EMN carried out the analyses and HBF made the figures.
234 MR, SHS, and EMN wrote the paper with input from all authors.

CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY

235 Software for the INLA methodology is available at R-INLA.org for the programming environment
236 R. INLA allows for fast Bayesian inference for latent Gaussian models such as the one described in
237 section 2. However, some modifications are required in order to ensure efficiency. First, the latent field
238 is of non-standard form since the mean vector and covariance matrix of the latent Gaussian field share
239 the same parameter H , and thus requires separate specification. Second, due to the LRD assumption,
240 the precision matrix, defined as the inverse covariance matrix, is dense and therefore unsuited for the
241 computationally efficient algorithms that INLA applies. In order to retain sparsity we have to introduce
242 an approximation such as that introduced by [Sørbye et al. \(2018\)](#). The model with these modifications

243 are available in the R-package `INLA.climate` which can be downloaded from the GitHub repository
244 `eirikmn/INLA.climate`.

245 The temperature data analyzed is downloaded from `https://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/`,
246 and the forcing data from `http://www.columbia.edu/~mhs119/Forcings/`.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. (A): Shows surface temperature anomalies for a grid point located around the city of Moscow (55N, 37E). The dotted blue line shows the estimated linear trend $m(t) = a + bt$ estimated using the method described in section 2, and the solid black curve is the estimated forced responses in Equation (7). (B): As in panel A, but for a location in the tropical Pacific ocean (33S, 120W).

Figure 2. Shows maps of estimates for the trend parameter b , and the noise parameters σ_ε and H for the time period 1900-2015. The presented estimates are the posterior means obtained from the estimated posterior marginal distributions. (A): Estimates of b using the methods described in section 2. (B): Estimates of b using the methods described in section 3. (C): Estimates of H using the methods described in section 2. (D): Estimates of H using the methods described in section 3. (E): Estimates of σ_ε using the methods described in section 2. (F): Estimates of σ_ε using the methods described in section 3.

Figure 3. The root mean square error (RMSE) as defined in Equation (8), measuring a standardized difference between the observed temperature signal and the trend model. (A): The RMSE for the model defined in section 2. (B): The RSME for the model defined in section 3.

Figure 4. The posterior probability of a positive linear trend given the observed temperature time series for each grid point. (A): For the time period 1900-1950 using the method described in section 2. (B): For the time period 1900-1950 using the method described in section 3. (C): For the time period 1900-1985 using the method described in section 2. (D): For the time period 1900-1985 using the method described in section 3. (E): For the time period 1900-2015 using the method described in section 2. (F): For the time period 1900-2015 using the method described in section 3.